

The star formation histories of massive quiescent galaxies

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The properties of the most massive galaxies provide fundamental constraints on both galaxy formation physics and cosmology. In the local Universe, it is well established that the most massive galaxies have long since shut down (quenched) their star-formation activity, exhibiting stellar population ages of order 10 billion years (Gyr). However, the extremely slow time-evolution of such ancient stellar populations prevents us from determining precise formation red-shifts (e.g., [1, 2, 3]).

Spectroscopic studies at redshift, $z = 1 - 2$ (8 - 9 Gyr ago) have long demonstrated that massive quiescent galaxies with ages of several Gyr already exist at this epoch, suggesting such objects trace their origins back to the first billion years of cosmic history [4, 5]. Recently, strong constraints on the properties of such objects have been achieved via full-spectral-fitting analyses that use high-SNR spectroscopy to break the age-metallicity-dust degeneracy that plagues photometric studies.

In [6, 7], we introduce a new method for fitting spectroscopic data, combining a flexible empirical model for the systematic uncertainties that arise during the observing process with a sophisticated physical model for the galaxies being observed. The method is implemented using the Bagpipes code [8]. An example galaxy fitted with this method is shown in Figure 1. The recovered star-formation history (SFH) is shown in the inset panel, demonstrating this galaxy formed at $z \sim 1.5$.

Studies such as this confirm the oldest quiescent galaxies at $z \sim 1 - 2$ had quenched by $z \sim 6$. However, even at $z \sim 2$, such objects are already too old to draw detailed conclusions about their evolution during the first billion years. These findings also highlight a clear gap in our knowledge, between massive star-forming galaxies at $z > 6$ and already-old quiescent galaxies at $z \sim 2$.

Recent studies have begun to bridge this gap, spectroscopically confirming the first massive quiescent galaxies at $z > 3$ (e.g., [9]). Such objects provide highly valuable insights into how baryonic feedback processes first began to arrest the extremely vigorous star formation observed in the earliest galaxies. However, the rarity, faintness and red colour of these objects make spectroscopic studies with existing instrumentation highly challenging. At present, only three secure spectroscopic red-

shifts exist for quiescent galaxies at $z > 3.5$ [10, 11]. These are based on low-SNR K -band data, which does not include the near-UV Balmer/4000Å break region critical for precise age determination (e.g., [12]), or the H α emission line critical for precise SFR determination.

To make further progress there is now an urgent need for the improved sensitivity and broader, redder wavelength coverage that can only be provided by the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST). This will allow the full spectral fitting methods recently proven at $z \sim 1 - 2$ to be extended, providing strong constraints on the SFHs and stellar metallicities of the earliest and most extreme massive quiescent galaxies, opening a new window on galaxy formation during the first billion years.

My JWST Cycle 1 program [13] will obtain deep NIRSpec spectroscopy of the highest-redshift known massive quiescent galaxy, GOODSS-9209 at $z = 4.657$ [14]. Figure 2 shows the SFH of GOODSS-9209. The top panel shows current constraints from photometric data. It can be seen that a range of different formation scenarios are consistent with photometric constraints, from slow, sustained star formation over ~ 1 Gyr to a monolithic collapse scenario over < 100 Myr. The constraints my NIRSpec data will provide are shown in the lower panel, along with mock spectroscopy from the JWST ETC. It can be seen that these new data will clearly distinguish between formation scenarios.

References

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Figure 1: A spectrum for an example galaxy is shown in blue, with the best-fitting Bagpipes model overlaid in orange. This analysis allows us to recover the SFH for this galaxy (inset panel), providing insights into the processes driving its evolution. Taken from [6].

Figure 2: The SFH of GOODSS-9209. Constraints from photometry are shown in gray. The shaded region is the 95 per cent confidence interval. Constraints from Bagpipes full spectral fitting of mock NIRSPEC data from my upcoming JWST program [13] are shown in blue. The mock data, shown in the inset, were generated with the JWST ETC using the dotted SFH as input. It can be seen that my NIRSPEC data will clearly distinguish between rapid, SMG-like and more gradual formation scenarios.